

Modular training resources for bioimage analysis

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Abstract

Modern microscopy enables us to measure structural and dynamical properties of many biological processes and is therefore an indispensable research tool. However, the amount and complexity of the produced imaging data is steadily increasing. Thus, handling the data as well as reproducibly and automatically extracting accurate scientific information requires dedicated “bioimage analysis” expertise. To facilitate the dissemination of this ubiquitously required expertise we developed an open-access bioimage analysis training resource. The resource is designed to help trainers to design and run courses on bioimage analysis for life scientists. The material is modular where each module covers one concise topic and provides corresponding activities. The activities can be executed using various popular software packages (e.g. ImageJ, Python). The material is hosted on a public software repository allowing the bioimaging community to readily contribute new training modules or improve existing modules. Within the last three years, the material has been used by several trainers in numerous courses and continuously improved.

Graphical abstract

Introduction

Microscopy is a key technology driving biological research and a large and diverse software ecosystem exists to analyse microscopy images. Software solutions can be open-source or commercial, and vary from general to specific use-cases, ease of use, levels of documentation, and accessibility (Haase *et al.*, 2022). Despite these available tools, the complexity and size of the corresponding imaging data can make it challenging to efficiently extract bio-physically meaningful information from the acquired images in a quantitative and reliable/reproducible manner. As a consequence, the bio-computational discipline “bioimage analysis” has emerged (GloBIAS, 2024, NEUBIAS, 2024). Scientists performing bioimage analysis have a diverse background and need to acquire a theoretical foundation on image formation as well as image processing and analysis algorithms. Furthermore, scientists must acquire the necessary skills to effectively and adequately use various software tools for image analysis tasks.

During the last decade, online resources for self-study have emerged in the form of videos, slides, interactive books, and Massive Open Online Courses (MOOCs) (e.g., (Bankhead, 2024, Haase, 2020, Image.sc, 2019, Seitz *et al.*, 2019, Jones *et al.*, 2022)). In addition, numerous in-person or online bioimage analysis courses have been delivered and sometimes recorded (e.g., (NEUBIAS, 2022, ZIDAS, 2024)). Live online or in-person courses are very valuable as they provide a platform for networking, interacting with expert trainers, and addressing specific

questions with respect to learners' needs. We found that an open-access resource allowing bioimage analysis trainers to efficiently design and deliver such courses to various target audiences would be helpful and is currently missing (Haase *et al.*, 2024, Sivagurunathan *et al.*, 2024). Such a resource should help and simplify the much-needed dissemination of bioimage analysis skills.

To address those needs we started in early 2019 to create an open-access online resource for bioimage analysis training accessible via <https://neubias.github.io/training-resources/> (Tischer *et al.*, 2024). Since then, this resource has been used in at least 25 courses with in total nearly 600 participants (Supplemental Table 1). With this publication we aim to further spread the use of this material and also kindly invite the bioimaging community to contribute to any aspect of this resource.

In the following sections we will describe the rationale, content, implementation details and usage instructions.

Training resource design and organization

We aimed for a resource to facilitate delivering in-person or online live courses. The material should include activities to illustrate use cases. Given the large number of image analysis software, we wanted to separate an activity from a particular software implementation. Finally, the material should allow bioimage analysts to tailor courses for different target audiences. This led to the following design constraints: open-access online hosting of the material, modularity, interactivity, usability within a live context, and easy extension by the community.

Design principles

We found that existing online material is primarily conceived as self-study resources and does not yet fulfil all our prerequisites. While a simple collection of slides could be used within a live teaching context, they are rather static, often lack integrated activities, and are hard to develop/maintain as a community. Pre-recorded videos are inappropriate for a live, interactive setting and also lack integrated activities. MOOCs provide comprehensive material often enriched with videos, exercises, and assessments that are best suited for self-paced study (Seitz *et al.*, 2019, Jones *et al.*, 2022). The interactive book by P. Bankhead (Bankhead, 2024) contains comprehensive explanations, example images, and activities, representing a good reference for bioimage analysis concepts. While all the aforementioned material are great resources, they impose a pre-defined order of topics and lack modularity. Modifications or additions of new concepts may therefore require major revisions; in addition, in our view, the existing resources are not designed to support agile contributions by a community of bioimage analysts.

We decided to base our training resource on the didactically excellent training material of *The Carpentries* (<https://carpentries.org/>) (Backhaus *et al.*, 2024, Brown *et al.*, 2023). A Carpentries expert has been a critical contributor to the initial development of the bioimage analysis training resource. Among other things, lessons by *The Carpentries* are aimed at novices as well as experts and gradually build knowledge, avoiding too much information at once. A lesson is composed of several so-called episodes, lasting for 20 to 60 minutes with clearly stated learning objectives. Each episode includes activities suited for live demonstration/live-coding, so to explain every step of the process, and formative assessments to identify misconceptions. *The Carpentries* provide a course on image-processing with python that can be used in a live context with a variety of example images and activities (Meysenburg *et al.*, 2023).

Our material differs from *The Carpentries'* primarily in its increased modularity and specific application to bioimaging data. Unlike *The Carpentries*, which delivers predefined lessons, we designed small, independent training modules (reminiscent to *Carpentries* episodes) that can be flexibly assembled into various courses — differing in length, target audience, and software packages covered (Fig. 1). To manage and optimize cognitive load (Sweller, 1988), each training “module” focuses on just one or very few new concepts that should be taught within 30-45 min. This inherently restricts the complexity or number of concepts included within a single module. A 'concept' in this context refers to a generic, commonly used principle or method in bioimage analysis that is agnostic to specific software implementations, such as 'object shape measurement'. A module is designed to provide all the necessary information to effectively motivate, explain (e.g., through figures, concept maps), and apply (e.g., using example images and code) its content.

Figure 1: Training resource design: Hierarchy of the bioimage analysis training course. A course is designed by assembling several existing modules. Each module explains a concept/method and provides activities. An activity has general instructions, an example image, and different software implementations.

Module structure

The above design principles, refined via repeated teaching of different modules, led to the subdivision of each module into nine distinct sections, as detailed in Figure 2 and Table 1. After the *Prerequisites* section, the following four sections (Fig. 2A-C) serve to teach the concept in a lecture style presentation, where the *Concept map* and a *Figure* are used as a visual support for the instructor to explain the concept to the learners. Some additional detailed explanations could be added after the main figure. The main section of a module is *Activities* that demonstrates different applications of the concepts that are taught in the module. Each activity is described in general software-agnostic terms and has linked example data that can be readily used. The instructor and learner can then select instructions for specific software packages (Fig. 2D, E). This separation of general concepts from specific implementations was a major design decision for this resource. This makes it possible to continuously add new software implementations of an activity, without needing to change much of the generic teaching content. In addition, this design also increases the didactic quality of the material, because it forces the trainer and students to disentangle universally applicable concepts and methods such as, e.g. “connected component analysis” and “object shape measurements”, from specific implementations such as ImageJ’s Particle Analyzer (Schneider et al., 2012) or scikit-image’s regionprops (van der Walt et al., 2014).

A Morphological filters

Prerequisites

Before starting this lesson, you should be familiar with:

- Segmentation overview
- Thresholding
- Connected component labeling
- Neighborhood filters

Learning Objectives

After completing this lesson, learners should be able to:

- Understand how to design morphological filters using rank filters
- Execute morphological filters on binary or label images and understand the output

Motivation

Morphological filters (MFs) are used to clean up segmentation masks and achieve a change in morphology and/or size of the objects. For example, MFs are used to remove wrongly assigned foreground pixels, separate touching objects, or identify objects boundaries.

B

C

D

Opening and closing of a binary image

- Open xy_8bit_binary_for_open_and_close.tif
- Perform erosion followed by dilation - opening. Explains its effects in removing small structures. If applicable show that opening runs as single command.
- Perform dilation followed by erosion - closing. Explains its effects on filling small holes, connecting gaps. If applicable show that opening runs as single command.

Show activity for:

```

skimage napari

# %% [markdown]
# ### Opening and closing of binary
#
# Part of teaching module [Morphological filtering](https://neubias.github.io/training-resources/filter_morphological/index.html#openClose)
# %%
# Import python packages.
from OpenJPEG import open_ij_tiff
from napari.viewer import Viewer
from skimage.morphology import square, disk
from skimage.morphology import erosion, dilation
  
```

E

F

Assessment

Fill in the blanks

Using those words fill in the blanks: closing, opening, min, shrinks, decreases, enlarges, max.

1. An erosion ____ objects in a binary image.
2. An erosion in a binary image ____ the number of foreground pixels.
3. A dilation ____ objects in a binary image.
4. An erosion of a binary image corresponds to a ____ rank operation.
5. An dilation of a binary image corresponds to a ____ rank operation.
6. A dilation followed by an erosion is called ____.
7. An erosion followed by a dilation is called ____.

```

Solution

1. shrinks
2. decreases
3. enlarges
4. min
5. max
6. closing
7. opening
  
```

Figure 2: Structure of a training module: This figure shows screenshots of a module website and activity. (A) Knowledge required to follow a given module is provided via links to other modules (*Prerequisites*). *Learning objectives* and *Motivation* provide the why and what will be learned during the module. The (B) *Concept Map* and (C) *Figure* visuals provide an overview of the key concepts. Additional explanations may appear after the main figure (not shown here). In *Activities* (D) the activity instruction and its implementations provide the necessary information to showcase a concept using a specific software (e.g. python and scikit-image/napari). (E) Example output generated when executing an activity. (F) Formative assessments are provided at the end of a module to reinforce what has been learned.

Module section	Explanation
Prerequisites	Contains links to other modules of our material, defining the content that learners should know before starting
Learning objectives	Defines the skills that learners will acquire
Motivation	Explains why it is important to acquire these skills
Concept map	A schematic drawing that defines the core new concepts that are taught
Figure	A figure illustrating the teaching content
Explanations (optional)	Additional details typically used to help self-study and add mathematical context
Activities	Interactive instructions for applying the concepts taught in various software platforms
Assessment	Questions and answers for testing the conceptual understanding
Follow-up material	Links to suitable follow-up training modules and extra-curricular material

Table 1: Training module sections: A training module is composed of difference sections to introduce the concept, provide examples, and further reading.

The subsequent “assessment” section (Fig. 2F) comprises short quizzes that allow the participants to test their understanding of the main concepts. For instance, a question and answer could be: “Q: What is the typical data type of a label mask image? A: Typically, label mask images are of positive integer data types (unsigned integer 8 or 16 bit) with zero being the background label”. Finally, the *Follow-up Material* section provides links to additional modules that can be learned after the current module or external resources.

In our experience, this predefined module structure significantly facilitates the addition of new material. While it still forces the contributor to carefully think about what they actually want to teach in the module, it frees one from thinking too much about how to structure and format the material.

Resource content

Over the last 5 years we created ~50 teaching modules (Supplemental table 2). Supplemental video 1-3 illustrate the content of the training material and how to teach a module.

The current material covers content typically taught in introductory and intermediate bioimage analysis courses. Among others, the resource includes modules on image data handling and the understanding of the different data formats, image data inspection, image filtering and

thresholding, segmentation and measurements, as well as basic scripting, batch processing, and cloud based computing. We also included so-called workflows, where learners, starting from example images, apply a sequence of methods to solve an image analysis task and obtain a result table. Finding suitable example image data for teaching a certain concept is a major effort. The repository contains small example image data that have been carefully selected to fulfil this need. The activities are designed for different levels of understanding and complexity.

A

B

C

<p>Basic Bioimage Inspection</p> <p>Learn to inspect your images and visualize your data.</p> <p>7 modules 5.25 hours 0.175 CP</p>	<p>Image Data Formats</p> <p>Learn how to open and handle different image data formats.</p> <p>5 modules 3.75 hours 0.125 CP</p>	<p>Basic Bioimage Analysis</p> <p>Learn essential concepts of image analysis, such as segmentation, intensity measurements, and filtering.</p> <p>12 modules 9 hours 0.3 CP</p>	<p>Basic Batch Analysis</p> <p>Learn how to automatically process image analysis tasks on multiple images.</p> <p>5 modules 3.75 hours 0.125 CP</p>
<p>Cloud Based Bioimage Analysis</p> <p>Learn about executing bioimage analysis on remote compute resources.</p> <p>2 modules 1.5 hours 0.05 CP</p>	<p>Bioimage Batch Analysis Essentials</p> <p>Crash course to learn the essentials of how to devise a basic image analysis workflow and how automatically apply it on multiple images.</p> <p>2 modules 3 hours 0.1 CP</p>	<p>ImageJ Macro</p> <p>Learn how to generate and modify scripts for image analysis workflows using the ImageJ macro language.</p> <p>8 modules 6 hours 0.2 CP</p>	

Figure 3: Module dependencies and courses: This figure shows screenshots of the resource home page. (A) Alphabetical list of modules. (B) Network of dependencies between modules. Each module is a node and the *Prerequisites* define the edges of the graph. By clicking on one of the nodes (arrow) the dependencies are highlighted (green). This information can be used to define a set of modules for a course. (C) Link to course suggestions that can

be taught using the training material. Each link leads to a course web page containing a list of sub-modules similar to what is shown in (A).

From the home page, modules can be accessed in an alphabetical order from the *Modules* navigator bar or shown as an overview (Fig. 3A). To execute an activity with a specific software the *Setup* navigator button leads to a *Tool installation* module that explains how to install the relevant software. The home page also provides a dynamic graph representation of the module dependencies (Fig. 3B). Using this graph one can navigate to the respective module or highlight dependencies. Seeing those dependencies facilitates bioimage analysts putting together a consistent course. For instance, if the goal of the course is for learners to be able to segment and quantify a noisy image (arrow in Fig. 3B), then the course should include convolutional filtering, object shape measurements, connected component analysis and other modules highlighted in green in Fig. 3B. The home page also provides a set of suggested courses, with their respective duration, number of modules, and number of ECTS credit (Fig. 3C). The courses have variable duration and range from understanding images and different image formats, up to bioimage analysis, batch processing and cloud computing. Clicking on a course opens a page with the modules to be taught within the course in their correct order; for longer course, there can also be an additional introductory overview module.

How to use the training resource

The resource is accessible from any browser via the site <https://neubias.github.io/training-resources/>. Between 2021 and 2024, the resource was used to conduct at least 25 courses (online and in person), involving nearly 600 participants and 14 distinct trainers (Supplemental Table 1). The training material has also been used to support scientific project discussions within an imaging facility context. By going through a set of specific modules relevant to the project, the bioimage analysis expert can help a facility user to clarify the questions, identify possible solutions, and eventually enable the facility user to solve the problem on their own.

How to run a course

Essentially, a course is a set of modules taught one after the other. In addition, it is recommended to plan an upfront trouble-shoot session to solve tool installation issues and a get-together session, where participants introduce themselves and describe their image analysis needs and motivation to join the course. At the end of the course, to further reinforce what has been learned, course organizers can plan an extra ½-1 day project time. During this time, learners apply what they learned in groups on selected projects.

In our hands, courses lasted between half a day to three days and include 3 to 18 teaching modules. Teaching one module took around 45 minutes such that, including breaks, about 6 modules could be taught in one day. An example of a three-day course is given in Table 2, see also past course schedules in the repository folder `courses` (Tischer et al., 2024). The choice of modules depends on the audience, the goal of the course, and the available time. To tailor

the course to the audience's needs one can ask participants to fill in a questionnaire at registration and/or ask to submit project slides. After identifying the course goal and level of the audience an instructor can use one of the consolidated courses as given on the home page of the training material (Fig. 3C) or design its own course. In the latter case, the dependency network (Fig. 3B) helps to identify a consistent sequence of modules, which can be shared with the learners as a document containing the links of the selected modules.

Day	Module title	Duration (min)	Link
Day 1	Trouble shoot tool installation	30-60	https://neubias.github.io/training-resources/tool_installation/
	General introduction	10	NA
	Digital image basics	45	https://neubias.github.io/training-resources/pixels/index.html
	Lookup tables	45	https://neubias.github.io/training-resources/lut/index.html
	Spatial image calibration	45	https://neubias.github.io/training-resources/spatial_calibration/index.html
	Project presentation	60	NA
	N-dimensional images	45	https://neubias.github.io/training-resources/multidimensional_image_basics/index.html
	Image data types	45	https://neubias.github.io/training-resources/datatypes/index.html
	Image projections	45	https://neubias.github.io/training-resources/projections/index.html
Day 2	Segmentation overview	10	https://neubias.github.io/training-resources/segmentation/index.html
	Manual thresholding	45	https://neubias.github.io/training-resources/binarization/index.html
	Automated thresholding	45	https://neubias.github.io/training-resources/auto_threshold/index.html
	Connected component labeling	45	https://neubias.github.io/training-resources/connected_components/index.html
	Object shape measurements	45	https://neubias.github.io/training-resources/measure_shapes/index.html
	Workflow: Basic 2D object analysis	45	https://neubias.github.io/training-resources/workflow_segment_2d_nuclei_measure_shape/index.html
Day 3	Object intensity measurements	45	https://neubias.github.io/training-resources/measure_intensities/index.html
	Image neighborhood filtering	45	https://neubias.github.io/training-resources/filter_neighbourhood/index.html
	Median filter	45	https://neubias.github.io/training-resources/median_filter/index.html

Local background subtraction	45	https://neubias.github.io/training-resources/local_background_correction/index.html
Morphological filters	45	https://neubias.github.io/training-resources/filter_morphological/index.html
Group work on projects	3 hours	NA

Table 2: Example 3-day course

How to teach a module

To teach a module both the instructor and the learners open the corresponding website. It can be useful to have two computer screens, one with the teaching material website and another with the software that is used to conduct the activities. Each module starts with a lecturing part, where the module web page is screen shared, followed by interactive activities where the software screen is shared. Using the sections on *Motivation* and *Learning Objectives* the instructor engages the audience by explaining in which context the module content is useful and which practical skills are going to be taught. The lecture continues, by explaining the main concepts, e.g., using a drawing board, discussing the module figure and/or the concept map.

Next, the conceptual knowledge is applied within one or more *Activites*. During the activity part the instructor shares the screen containing the respective software tool. The module web page is best kept on a separate screen and is used to guide the instructor throughout the activity. Images can be drag and dropped or downloaded from the module web site to the respective software. The pace of the activity should be slow enough so that learners can click-along (for a GUI based software) or type-along (for coding). This allows the instructor to provide additional explanations on the different commands and learners to slowly deepen their understanding on a practical level (Brown et al., 2023). Finally, learners could test their conceptual understanding using the respective assessment sections or performing additional activities on their own. On the home page of the training resource, we provide links to videos showcasing the teaching of a module.

For online teaching, we found that it is hard for learners with only one screen to click-along or type-along. In this case it is best to showcase the activity and ask the learners to either repeat the activity or perform the subsequent activity. In this situation it is important to leave enough time for feedback at the end of each activity.

For more detailed guidance, please refer to our `TEACHING_TIPS.md` in the GitHub repo (Tischer et al., 2024).

How to contribute

The implementation of the training resource relies on modified code from *The Carpentries* for building the training module websites (<https://neubias.github.io/training-resources/index.html>). All raw material and source code is hosted on GitHub <https://github.com/NEUBIAS/training-resources/> (Tischer et al., 2024) enabling collaborative development by a wide community. Using Jekyll (Jekyll, 2024), all modules are converted to

HTML and can be accessed by any common web browser (Fig. 2 and 3). The material is CC-BY licensed such that it can be re-used freely with acknowledgement of the original source. GitHub issues are used for discussions about adding new material or improvements of the current content. For example, <https://github.com/NEUBIAS/training-resources/issues/256> features an interesting discussion on how to explain the "watershed" algorithm. Pull requests streamline the review and integration of new content. Contributors can not only develop new or enhance existing modules, but also provide valuable resources like example images and ideas for additional activities. Details about how to contribute are documented in `CONTRIBUTING.md` in the GitHub repo (Tischer et al., 2024).

Discussion and outlook

Currently, existing online material mainly focuses on self-study, lacks modularity, does not allow to flexible reorganize topics, and is typically hard to further develop by the community, e.g., (Bankhead, 2024, Haase, 2020, Image.sc, 2019, Seitz et al., 2019, Jones et al., 2022, Meysenburg et al., 2023).

Our training resource aims to complement existing material by supporting instructors in delivering live courses. The courses address researchers at the level of master or above that want to solve bioimage analysis problems. Live courses allow for networking, interactivity with the instructors and other learners, as well as project work. Our resource has been used by numerous trainers to educate hundreds of students over several years. Its modular structure offers several practical benefits. On multiple occasions, we used the resource to provide supporting information during project discussions between bioimage analysts and their collaborators.

As individual units, modules can be easily added or updated without disrupting the overall structure, making contribution by the community easy. While careful consideration should be given to how new material aligns with existing content, minor overlaps can be accommodated. This modularity also simplifies course preparation for multiple trainers, as each can focus solely on their assigned modules. Given the streamlined nature of each module, the preparation effort for a trainer is minimal. This is a significant advantage, as it facilitates the onboarding of new trainers and contributes to expanding the global bioimage analysis teaching workforce.

The focus on software agnostic modules makes it possible to use the same training material to design various courses, targeting different audiences, and using different software. For instance, both researchers working with point scanning fluorescence microscopy or with colour camera based histological imaging data will need to know the content of the "digital image" module and also more advanced modules such as "distance transform" or "object shape measurements" are likely relevant to both audiences. However, while the concept of "colour space" is critical for histological imaging data it is irrelevant for fluorescence data. Thus, when creating a course for researchers working with histological data, it may only be necessary to add a new module about

“colour space” and some new activities about RGB images in the existing “datatypes” module, while many other parts of the course could be covered with existing modules.

Our approach also has disadvantages when compared to others. Our material emphasizes examples and practical application over exhaustive completeness or deep mathematical details. As a module covers the theoretical foundations of a topic only very concisely, learners will need to run some of the activities to gain a deeper understanding. This makes self-study harder, as learners might miss crucial context and explicitly need a software installation.

A further challenge of our modular approach is deciding on the **granularity of teaching content**. This means carefully assessing what to include in one module versus splitting into several. This decision impacts how **appealing the material is to different trainers and audiences**. While our framework allows modules to **co-exist, even with redundant content**, we've avoided duplication so far. However, this might become an option if it makes the resource more attractive to a wider audience.

We are aware that the topics covered by our training material only address a minor fraction of the bioimage analysis field. The choice of topics has a bias towards light microscopy, reflecting the fact that many of the authors work within a light microscopy facility. Nevertheless, we believe that we do cover the essentials. The topics taught by other resources mainly cover “data handling” skills (e.g. opening, saving, inspecting, dealing with different data structures and formats), and skill on how to extract quantitative data from the images (e.g. filtering, segmentation, object shape and intensity measurements) (Haase, 2020, Seitz et al., 2019, Jones et al., 2022, Meysenburg et al., 2023). Thus, there seems to be an agreement among the community as what is considered an essential bioimage analysis skill. Indeed, a fraction of our modules is already sufficient to cover these essential topics.

We do not want to limit our resource to essential topics and are continuously working on new material and courses. Image acquisition and degradation is relevant to assess the reliability of the measurements. For instance, although you can measure object shapes, one should be aware of the resolution limit and which metrics are still reliable. Currently, we only have the module “Fluorescence microscopy image formation” on this topic and we are working on adding more modules on image formation (e.g. resolution, signal to noise, channel crosstalk, tiled acquisition) and degradation (e.g. spherical, chromatic, stitching artefacts), and how those may affect image analysis. One important aspect of bioimage analysis is the validation of the results and currently we only have one module titled “Batch exploration of segmentation results” on this topic. In the context of machine learning, one would require for example quantitative comparison with ground truth data. We also miss modules to quantify colocalization and co-occurrence, a topic dear to molecular biologists; we also currently miss modules on tracking. We are developing modules to introduce students to machine learning based methods for segmentation, image classification and image restoration. Due to the ever-increasing amount and complexity of image data we are also working on adding more modules and eventually a course related to image data management. Thus, much training material could and should be added. In this context we would like to emphasise again that the modular open-access nature of

our resources facilitates and invites addition of missing material by the growing community of bioimage analysts.

Our resource mainly concentrates on ImageJ and Python implementations for the activities. However, there are many other open-source image analysis software (e.g. Icy, Cellprofiler, Knime) and commercial software (e.g. Matlab, Arivis, Imaris). It would be nice to add additional software implementations and this is readily possible without disruption the existing material.

An important aspect of the resources is suitable example image data, which is currently hosted in the same GitHub repository as the training material. While this is convenient it does not allow to host large image data. We are therefore considering for the future to host training image data on an image repository, e.g. the BioImage Archive (EMBL-EBI, 2024).

In conclusion, the presented resource with its modularity allows to teach an evolving field such as bioimage analysis. The resource has been used to teach students at different levels by multiple trainers in various courses and we are positive that the training content and also the number of trainers will keep increasing in the coming years. We therefore foresee our open-access resource to make a valuable contribution to satisfying the global need for bioimage analysis courses.

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Supplemental material

The supplemental material is available at: **Preprint**

Supplemental Table 1: List of courses 2021-2024

The table lists courses that have being held in the last 4 years using the bioimage analysis training resources.

Supplemental Table 2: List of modules

The table lists all the consolidated modules in the resource.

Supplemental Video 1: Bioimage analysis training resource: How to

A video illustrating how to navigate through the website of the training resource.

Supplemental Video 2: Digital image basics: Introduction

Video showing the teaching of the module *Digital image basics*.

Supplemental Video 3: Digital image basics: 2d python

Video showing the teaching of the first activity in the module *Digital image basics*.